

The 2-step informed consent tool: A manual.

Authors: Matthias Kaiser, Marjo Rauhala, Jonas Pfister, Vasiliki Mollaki.

Contributors: NCSR-D; LMU; UM; UEFST; UNIBUC; UNIWA; UCILeR; RUG; K&I; KIT; UB; IEA; KUL; UB.

To be cited as: Kaiser, M., Rauhala, M., Pfister, J., Mollaki, V. (2026). "The 2-step Informed Consent tool: A Manual"; CHANGER Project, working documents.

This is the abbreviated version of the concept note on 2-step Informed Consent Process. For all deeper explanatory context we refer to its concept note. In this practical manual we shall focus on the What-to-do, Why-to-do-it, How-to-do-it, and Who's-going-to-do-it, with only the bare essentials, capturing the idealized abstract standard cases. We are going to present a methodology – or a tool if you prefer – to assess the ethical challenges when traditional informed consent seems not adequate to cover the future uses of the data or samples. We call it the “2-step Informed Consent Process” or “2ICP” for short.

Whom do we address? Who is the target audience?

This tool addresses the research practitioners and the ethical committees. It relates to the permission for uncertain primary uses and secondary research use that a patient gives when donating a blood- or cell sample or other sensitive data for research.

Purpose and Scope

The purpose of the following manual is to provide an outline of a consent procedure that bridges the gap between what can be specified in a primary consent form for a specific use and the secondary assessment of an ethical committee (REC) of a biobank which relates to uses that could not be specified in the primary consent. The REC is typically installed by a national, European or international biobank. The biobanks can be non-profit or for-profit biobanks. The scope is for all adult consent and for re-consent in paediatric biobanks after becoming 15 years. The age-group below that limit is not covered here.

Approach for Work Package and Relation to other Work Packages and Deliverables

The document is part of WP3 and is one of the tools / methodologies which are developed in that WP. Here the short Manual for practical uses is presented. Its motivation is initiated from the call for this research project, and the interpretation of the specific challenges that were discussed with the whole consortium. As all the tools developed in WP3, this one is inspired by the results of WP2, and the concrete experiences of the contributors. It falls under the general framework text in Deliverable 3.1 is believed to be original and innovative. WP4 and WP5 are intended to follow up some of the related issues.

Methodology and Structure of the Deliverable

The methodology used here is mainly philosophical and interdisciplinary as it tries to combine insights from ethics, law, and social sciences, and translate them to possible uses in medical science and health care. The text starts out with general constraints that the tool needs to implement before it moves on to a sketch of practical applications. The text provides the principle pillars of such applications while it leaves some practical aspects open for the context of the users.

The Manual

Note that this manual will be supplemented by a (published) concept note.

When to use the 2-step consent procedure? What are the typical topics?

What is the adequate ethical interface between donor and stem cell banks? How can informed consent work here? There are a legal dimension and a social dimension to be observed. The problem is that the initial informed consent is for a specific research use, while secondary uses by a biobank cannot be specified. While one may consent to the generation of stem cells, the consent does not foresee what the biobank does with them and what projects they are sold to.

Often the donors may act on trust that the cell- or blood sample will be used for “good” research tasks. However, such trust may easily be shattered if they learn through the media what kind of research modern medicine is engaged in. They may find some of these research tasks “outrageous” or simply unethical. It is important to maintain the trust of the public and their willingness to contribute to research. Therefore, one wants to try to optimize donor’s consent in a way that provides them some kind of influence also over the secondary uses administered by biobanks.

There are general ethical principles which are recognized as important in this context. In regard the donors one wants to protect:

- **autonomy,**
- **dignity,**
- **justice,**
- **privacy,**
- **data protection,**
- **informed consent.**

In regard the science using stem cells one is concerned about:

- **freedom of research,**
- **social responsibility of research,**
- **benefits for better / improved health care,**
- **new medical technologies, including personalized medicine,**
- **new transplantation opportunities.**

A theoretical Framework: On Value Sensitive Designs

(ref.: Friedman, B., & Hendry, D. G. (2019). *Value sensitive design: Shaping technology with moral imagination*. Mit Press.)

Our suggested approach to the issue is inspired by what is commonly called **Value Sensitive Design (VSD)** which has been suggested as a proactive tool for innovation and technology development (f. ref.). The methodology is spun around the concept of Ethics-by-Design and the idea that high-level and abstract principles are not really useful for assessments that truly capture the lived experience with moral choices that involved

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, under grant agreement No 101131683.

actors relate to. It is, therefore, a stakeholder (donor) centric approach that aims at mirroring their values. Crucial steps are, thus, the adequate representation of the stakeholder, a practice (narrative) understanding of which values might be relevant for them and attempt to manage potential value conflicts and trade-offs. Obviously, these deliberations are not (fully) determined by high-level law or abstract philosophical reasoning. The challenge for research is to offer the stakeholders (donors) choices and values which communicate well and release their active moral sentiment.

It is, then, only on this basis that a secondary ethics committee may decide on the use of the stem cells in the biobank. The stakeholder input operates then as a general constraint to the ethical clearance of research projects with these stem cells.

How do we do the 2-step consent in practice? Planning and execution.

The first step is to agree to a standard informed consent form. Since the donor may not know what (human) pluripotent stem cells are and what function they have for the human development they need factual information in understandable common language: Provide an accepted and understandable plain language definition of PSCs.

The second step is to provide easy-to-understand relevant information about pluripotent stem cells in terms of what they can do and how they are sourced.

The third step is to agree to the condition that the donor’s tissue / cell sample will be subject to an ethical assessment by a named and independent ethics committee before its hPSCs are released for further research.

There are different suggestions how this can be done. One way is to name a proxy representative in the committee to be informed about one’s values and ethical viewpoints.

However, given the distance between a concrete donor and an international member of such an ethics committee, this seems hugely impracticable. Another way is to provide more general information of the patient’s value-landscapes to the committee being involved in the second step assessment. These values are then to restrict the outcome of the assessment in the committee. We suggest here this method.

Therefore, the fourth step is to constrain the committee’s final judgement by a ranked list of basic values and ethical principles of the original donor, as specified in the informed consent form. Such a list may have the following form:

Here is a possible example of such a list:

<i>Value / principle</i>	<i>Explanation</i>	<i>Rank: *, **, ***, ?</i>	<i>Comment</i>
Respect for human dignity	Avoid outcomes which threaten human autonomy or the place of humans in society / nature.		
Beneficence	Fight diseases and improve public health		
Non-maleficence	Follow the no-harm principle, and potential benefits need always to trump the risks		
Justice	Strive for a fair distribution of risks and benefits, with special attention to the most vulnerable and to global justice between North and South		
Privacy and confidentiality	Protecting personal information of donors, and inhibiting retracting (genetic) characteristics to donor; anonymized.		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, under grant agreement No 101131683.

Transparency	All research with sample needs to be open research, available to the scientific community in all steps and funding information		
Accountability	All research parties / institutions need to be accountable for their actions and results, follow ethical guidelines, and be liable for harm.		
Social responsibility	The research needs to address real social needs and pressing problems, rather than short term economic interests.		
Trustful relations	The idea that humans are social beings and are not able to survive in solitude, we trust that parents will take care of their children to grow up well. Trust between persons takes normally some time to develop, but it can be lost in an instant.		
Solidarity	All research efforts need to be guided by solidarity with weak societal groups and the improvement of the vulnerable.		
Autonomy	Respect the right and freedom of every individual to make own choices.		
Inclusiveness and care	Show empathy for suffering people and include them in your treatment efforts.		
Peace	Make sure your research is not contributing to warfare but serves peaceful purposes.		
Sustainability	In your research do not exploit natural resources and do not diminish biodiversity.		

Move from concept to “narrative”.

There is a justified worry that the presentation of such a list with concepts and brief explanations, supplemented by the instruction to rank them, may constitute an intellectual difficulty for the donor. How can they translate these values to real-life situations? In particular, would they be able to foresee possible value conflicts and would they be able to suggest value trade-offs?

The way around this would be to prepare small narratives which explain the values in contexts which are recognizable for the donor. Sometimes, even an illustration can achieve this. We shall here only provide some illustrative examples how this could be achieved. However, one can expect both national and cultural differences in regard to what narrative / illustration really triggers the moral sentiment of the donor.

By way of example, we provide some ideas:

- **“Respect for human dignity”**: ”You should grant your fellow humans the same rights and privileges that you believe you have simply because you are born into this world. You are an individual in human society who has a right to have the basic human needs satisfied (shelter, food, health etc) and who should be treated by others, be they persons, authorities or states, in ways that do not compromise the integrity of your being. While you probably can enumerate many examples where this norm is disrespected in our world, you will rarely anybody who would not appeal to this value as a normative expectation from all others. It is always hard to define precisely what the norm contains of positive expectations, but most people will be able to identify when it is broken.”
Possible illustration:

- **“Justice”**: This a value that relates to how (groups of) individuals are treated and how they treat each other mutually. It is a relational property between all those who fall under the concept of human dignity. A common misunderstanding is that justice means equality. This is not the case, our societies and cultures are diverse and so are our living conditions, not everyone can have the same share of the common goods as others. But it relates to equity. This means that the chances of access to common goods should as far as possible be similar. An illustration expresses this idea well:

- **“Trustful relations”**: Humans are an *altricial* species, from birth on they need the care of others to grow up to adults. They are also social beings, meaning that their basic needs in life are typically taken care of through the relationships with others. One rule in many (indigenous and other) societies, is the rule of reciprocity: you offer some good to someone, and implicitly there is an expectation that this person will do the same to you. You this an expectation of future reliable collaboration towards a common good. This can, of course, be disappointed. But often our interactions are built on the trust that the other can be relied upon to support us. We have established a trustful relation. See e.g.:

- “**Beneficence**”: This is a common expectation in health care and medicine. It is a description that the outcome of some actions should be experienced as **doing good** from the patients’ perspective. It does not really matter whether this is part of a professional expectation / duty or part of charity or simply private friendship. Since virtually all of our actions imply some costs (not necessarily in an economic sense), beneficence means that the sum of all aspects / outcomes of our actions should be a positive result for those who are targeted by our actions.

Now, assuming we have explained the list of relevant values to the donors and they are aware of the nature and possible uses of hPSCs, the next task would be to explain that sometimes some of these good values may come into conflict with the other values and we have to make a difficult choice. We need to prioritize. We can provide examples for the donor. For instance: Beneficence may come into conflict with justice. Assume we could “build” an important organ like the human heart from hPSCs it could save many lives by a heart transplantation with heart created by precision medicine. The benefit for the patient is clear. But is this a just addition to our health system? It will be so expensive that not many will be able to receive it, and certainly not the many people with a serious heart condition in the Global South. Would it then not be better to use the resources for the development of a potentially more equitable medical intervention?

Who is doing the 2-step consent in practice? The independent ethics committee.

In the final step, the sale and use in further research of the hPSCs is decided by an independent and broadly composed multidisciplinary (with social science and humanities / ethics reps) committee. The committee tries to respect patients' values as much as practically possible.

Conclusions

WP3 presents this 2-step procedure as a tool which scientists, medical researchers and ethical experts may want to try out in practice. It is an “incomplete” tool in the sense that it would need to be adjusted to the local / regional / cultural context while maintaining the principle leading ideas. Further research is needed to judge its benefits and shortcomings.

-----End of Document-----

